

WOODRISE 2022

RENOVATION, RESTORATION & REHABILITATION
OF URBAN BUILDINGS USING WOOD BASED TECHNOLOGIES

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Bioinspired Living Coating System for High-Rise Buildings

Anna Sandak^{1,2}

¹ *InnoRenew CoE, Izola, Slovenia, anna.sandak@innorenew.eu*

² *Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies,
University of Primorska, Koper, Slovenia, anna.sandak@famnit.upr.si*

Several tall buildings have achieved greater heights and their designs have become more attractive and complex. Consequently, access and maintenance of building façade has become more demanding in terms of efficiency, coordination, and customisation. Architectonic coatings enhance the functional and aesthetical durability of degradable materials by protecting their surface against environmental and biotic degradation. Therefore, paint and coating applied on the exterior of a residence, or a commercial building, not only add to the aesthetics of the building but also protect it against heat, UV, harsh winters, soaking rain, and other adverse weather conditions. Hence, the service life of architectural coatings significantly impacts the overall building maintenance costs.

The deterioration process of bio-based building materials (timber, engineered wood products) exposed to weathering mainly affects aesthetical properties. In most cases, weathering is caused by abiotic factors and manifests as an alteration in color, surface cracking, change in glossiness, and increased surface roughness. The intensity and extent of weathering depend on the local macro-, meso-, and microclimate conditions, weather history, material type, architectural details, and specific surface properties. The most important factors that affect weathering kinetics are solar radiation and stresses imposed by the cyclical wetting (moisture), together with changes in temperature, environmental pollutants, and the actions of certain microorganisms. In general, unprotected raw bio-based materials weather faster on the subsurface, leaving the bulk intact. Differences in discoloration may be very noticeable on the same façade, especially on buildings where water and solar radiation are not spread uniformly across the surface (Sandak et al. 2019).

To broaden their applicability, an overall improvement of several properties of bio-based materials, such as dimensional stability, thermal stability, fire resistance, biotic and abiotic degradation resistance, and mechanical properties, is required. Protection methods include environmentally friendly bulk treatments, such as thermal treatments, densification, impregnation, and chemical modifications as well as surface treatments, including innovative coatings, impregnations, or integration of developments in nanotechnology to protect biomaterials. The latest trends are driven by the biomimicry approach of capturing and exploiting properties that have evolved in nature, which is also the inspiration for ARCHI-SKIN. This project will implement biomimetic principles for the development of Smart Living Surfaces (SLS), where a living coating system will be designed and implemented for the protection of various building materials. Such an approach allows for the derivation of optimal designs that benefit from improvements made during the

evolution of living organisms and efficient use of natural resources in a more sustainable and environmentally friendly manner.

The coating formulation will be optimized for three types of substrates: bio-based porous, inorganic porous, and non-porous (Fig.1). Both organic and inorganic (wood, modified wood, concrete, stone, and bricks) porous materials, will be filled with various carbon sources that will serve as nutrients, and selective bio-additives that will stimulate microbial growth, control cell morphology, and Extracellular Polymeric Substances (EPS) matrix production. Additionally, biological materials will be impregnated with environmentally friendly fire and flame retardants. For non-porous materials (metal, plastic), the coating system formulation will contain a higher content of modified lignin. Thanks to various natural additives as well as the presence of living fungal cells, the ARCHI-SKIN coating system will possess several innovative properties such as self-regeneration and bioremediation.

Figure 1: ARCHI-SKIN project concept

Application of ARCHI-SKIN coating in big cities will potentially contribute to lowering air pollution, a major global urban challenge resulting in an estimated extra 800,000 deaths a year in Europe (Lelieveld et al. 2019). The enhancement in performance due to self-repair functionality will improve the environmental impact and reduce the cost burden of premature failure in service and maintenance activity. Superior service life performance is particularly relevant in tall structures, where regular maintenance and renovation are more time consuming and costly. Improvements in quality of materials that reduce the cost of recoating over decades should, therefore, be economically attractive for architects, building owners, and ultimate users.

Keywords: architectonic coatings, durability, smart living surfaces, engineered living materials, building façade

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